

Counter-Hegemonic Cartographies as Tools for Ensuring Rights: A Case Study of the Banhado Community in São José dos Campos, SP

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This paper recounts the ongoing threat of eviction faced by the Favela do Banhado community in São José dos Campos, Brazil, and highlights the collaborative endeavors between the university and the community in generating geospatial data and techno-political support to develop a popular land regularization plan. Notably, it focuses on the use of unmanned aerial vehicles for data collection to reconstruct the cartography of the area, which is absent from official records.

The exclusionary and unequal nature of the urbanization process in Brazil has led to cities burdened with problems such as a lack of basic sanitation, schools, healthcare facilities, public transportation, and housing. Favelas, as significant spatial expressions of this process, emerge from informal settlements without proper technical standards and financial resources and currently house approximately 11.4 million people, which accounts for 6% of the country's population (IBGE, 2010). The demand for cartographic representations that capture and measure the specificities of this phenomenon at various scales (national, regional, municipal, and local), considering social, biophysical, construction, and topographic aspects, is closely linked to the realization of rights through land regularization and urban development. However, favelas are often excluded from systematic cartography, zoning maps, and master plans. This exclusion not only reflects the lack of interest from the government in understanding and addressing the needs of this population but also leads to physical barriers and concealment aimed at denying and hiding their reality.

In general, favelas are excluded from cartography, including zoning maps and master plans. This cartographic exclusion is often accompanied by physical barriers and concealment, such as the construction of walls and fences, which aim to deny and hide these communities from the larger society. In some instances, the government actively works towards the exclusion of favelas, as seen in the case of Rio de Janeiro, where the municipality requested the removal of favelas from Google Maps to present a city without slums for the 2014 World Cup. These actions were accompanied by concrete

measures such as evictions, repossessions, and the "pacification" of favelas like Complexo do Alemão and Maré, along with other communities (PITILLO, 2014). Mapping conducted by Faulhaber et al. (2015) demonstrated how risky area cartography narratives favored the removal of communities in areas of great interest to the real estate market. In the pre-Olympic context, 67,000 people were forced to move, more than the combined number of removals by Pereira Passos and Lacerda.

Paraphrasing Maricato (2001), multiple factors determine whether a community will be included or excluded from maps. One key factor is when the location of a favela becomes valuable to the real estate market, leading to mapping not for the purpose of guaranteeing rights but rather to justify removals. In a period where urban interventions are increasingly driven by urban entrepreneurialism, with the state as an active agent in promoting urban economic development through attracting real estate investments, cartography plays a fundamental role. It spatially materializes the technical discourse that justifies often violent state actions against these communities.

In this context, it is ethically imperative to ensure that threatened communities not only have the right to dispute the narratives of facts and make their reality visible but also have the right to present alternative planning that acknowledges them as rights holders and not objects of a neoliberal urbanization model. Considering this narrative, this article discusses an experience by the Urbanism Teaching, Research, and Extension Practices (PExURB) group from the Institute of Architecture and Urbanism at USP São Carlos, in collaboration with the Federal University of Bahia (UFBA) and Vale do Paraíba University (Univap) and the NGO Veracidade. The project involves professors, architecture and urban planning students, and environmental and civil engineers working with the residents of a community in São José dos Campos to develop an urban design project and a popular plan to support land regularization, supported by the concepts of counter-hegemonic Cartography.

John Brian Harley, a seminal figure in the history and philosophy of cartography, introduced the notion that a map is not an objective and neutral image of reality. Maps accumulate omissions, intentions, values, errors, and ideologies, and conceal a set of power relations shaped by individuals, the market, and often the State (HARLEY, 2001). It is on this conceptual basis that counter-cartography emerges, with social or participatory cartography as its derivative. Counter-cartography aims to deconstruct the political and economic logic of certain organizations, mechanisms, and social hierarchies. It sheds light on contradictions and invisibilities while reshaping the image of the official map and the domination interests associated with cartography (MESQUITA, 2013). In other words, "counter-cartography is less a visual object that accumulates information and more an opportunity to go beyond the representation itself, generating dialogues and discoveries, potentiating narratives along with interventions in public spaces" (MESQUITA, 2013, p.177).

In Brazil, since the 1990s, there has been a notable increase in exemplary experiences of including local populations in mapping practices (ACSELRAD, 2010). This is due to the diversification of spatial representation forms and the emergence of supporting technologies such as geotechnologies and remotely piloted aircraft systems (RPAS). Heterogeneous sectors and actors, including NGOs, universities, environmental organizations, and associations of quilombolas and indigenous communities, actively contest the influence of official and dominant knowledge in the narrative arena, crystallizing a new axis in cartographic representation. This axis establishes relationships "between representational languages and territorial practices, between the legitimacy of subjects in cartographic representation and their power effects on the territory" (ACSELRAD, 2010, p.9).

As highlighted by Moore and Garzón (2010), in recent years, counter-mapping has increasingly become a key and alternative strategy for assessing and communicating issues related to environmental justice, public health, urban planning, and human rights. By mapping their absences (such as fundamental rights like housing and access to basic sanitation services) and demands for land and territory, communities or other social groups can expose specific contexts and problems they face, articulate and demand solutions, and support actions aimed at implementing public policies. In an interesting reference, Da Silva and Shaw (2011) documented and explored, in the paper "Cartography of the Favela," the issues of violence, inequality, and internal dynamics within favelas in Recife and Olinda, using the lens of counter-cartography.

The Banhado favela faces the same processes. Located in the central region of São José dos Campos, the Banhado community encompasses established territorial relations that have been in place for over 80 years. The community consists of two residential nuclei: Núcleo I, a more densely populated area occupied by rural workers attracted to industrial job opportunities between 1960 and 1980, and Núcleo II, characterized by scattered areas of small farms occupied by small-scale farmers since the 1930s (Alberini, 2015). In both cases, the residents have close ties to the city center in terms of using public services, employment, and the commercialization of agricultural products. The population occupies an area of approximately 255,000 square meters and consists of around 460 families, totaling about 2,000, but they never appeared in the official maps (Figure 1).

Figure1: Cartographic Plan of the State of São Paulo disregarding the occupation of the community of Banhado. Scale 1:1000. Source: Geographic and Cartographic Institute (1978).

According to Ab'Saber (1991), the Banhado area in São José dos Campos is an amphitheater-shaped meandering excavation basin that originated from the geomorphological formations of Tremembé and São José dos Campos (Paraíba do Sul River floodplain system extending between the cities of Jacareí and Cachoeira Paulista). The slope that characterizes the amphitheater is approximately 50 meters high and separates the city center from Jardim Nova Esperança. The area is characterized by significant vegetation and constitutes a vast green area considered a city landmark.

These characteristics make the Banhado region strategically valuable for the real estate market and revitalization projects, excluding the interests and rights of the resident community. In general, official cartography, both systematic and thematic, has little or no representation of the Banhado community throughout its existence. This was accompanied by a regulatory process driven by a series of environmental and social conflicts, resulting in a slow but continuous process of eviction of residents.

In the 1970s, the Banhado area became the subject of specific interventions due to its geographic and environmental aspects. In the second Master Plan, developed by the office of Jorge Wilhelm, the Banhado area was characterized as a large regional park, providing a viewpoint for the foothills of the Mantiqueira Mountains. The existence of the community was denied both in the plan and on the plan's maps. Subsequently, State Law No. 11.262/2002 (Banhado Environmental Protection Area) followed the same path, presenting general restrictions, with no management plan developed to this day.

Since the 2000s, the Municipality of São José dos Campos has implemented initiatives to isolate the community by cutting off public services, blocking access roads, and encouraging residents to leave. Social facilities in the area, such as the healthcare and dental treatment center and the Hélio Augusto de Souza Foundation, which offered technical courses for children and adults, were deactivated and/or demolished by the municipality. It is important to note that this is not an isolated initiative but part of a strategy to remove approximately twenty favelas from central areas to peripheral regions of São José dos Campos and establish a structured road network that attracts and stimulates real estate development in the municipality. Considering these initiatives, the community of Banhado organized itself to propose alternatives and, above all, resist a costly urbanization model favored by the government but contrary to the needs of the residents.

To assist the Banhado community in proposing an alternative to eviction through a Popular Land and Urban Development Plan, an aerial survey using a remotely piloted aircraft system (RPAS) was adopted as part of the data acquisition phase. The chosen RPAS was a DJI Phantom 4 Pro equipped with a 20 MP CMOS sensor camera and an f/2.8 aperture lens. The RPAS survey aimed to obtain an aerial photogrammetric base to create planimetric, cadastral, and thematic maps. This approach was the most viable in terms of technical and financial aspects, as it provided a cost-effective solution that allowed the development of cartographic material using images with a spatial resolution of approximately three centimeters and planimetric accuracy superior to freely available satellite images.

For the flight operation, the team, supported by the local community representatives, developed a methodology that included seven flight plans organized using the Pix4D Capture application to cover the entire extensive area to be surveyed (approximately 58.4 hectares). The team's main concerns during the flight planning were weather conditions, flight duration due to the limited battery autonomy (approximately 23 minutes), and ensuring the safety of team members and third parties during the

activity. The flight was conducted at an average altitude of 80 meters with an 80% overlap of lateral and longitudinal photos. After the image acquisition phase, the data went through a processing phase with transformations applied based on the Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) method. By merging all flights and processing the images using Agisoft PhotoScan software, the final products were an orthomosaic, a 3D model, and contour lines with a 1-meter equidistance. The production of the mosaic represented a shift in the production of spatial information, enabling community access to aerial photogrammetry. This marked an important step in the participatory planning process by providing a broad and detailed view of Banhado.

In conjunction with field surveys, the aerial imagery, supported by QGIS, allowed the vectorization of plots and their construction characteristics, including areas that were inaccessible during the fieldwork (Figure 2). Roads, as well as sewage ditches and channels, were delineated and prioritized, along with identifying areas of risk. These cartographic representations have been essential in helping both the professionals involved in the Popular Plan and the community counter the arguments presented by the local government for the removal of their homes. This counterpoint is facilitated by the fact that the community now possesses more detailed maps, which were previously in the hands of the municipality.

Figure 2: Development of aerial survey and multifunctionality technical cadastral activities in the community during the month of January 2019.

Additionally, a multifunctional technical registry was created (Figure 3), considering variables such as employment, access to education, leisure, and mobility, as well as the importance of Banhado for the residents' food security. These variables were often overlooked in the registries prepared by the government.

Figure 3: Sample of field data and information from the Banhado community spatialized in a thematic map

According to Fantin et al. (2018), using RPAS for more accessible surveys provides a detailed physical base for social participation, bringing the community closer to the development of the land and urban regularization plan and contributing to the reversal of technology's role in society. The high level of detail obtained through aerial surveys with RPAS allows for discussions regarding strategies for remaining in a location with geological and geotechnical risks, debates on relocating housing in such areas and defining road layouts that enable the structuring of urban services such as electricity, water, sewage, and the location of public facilities. In this sense, by actively involving the community in the project's development, RPAS has proven to be a powerful instrument with remarkable potential for social impact. Building on this assumption, the next stage of the work will involve using the orthomosaic and the already-produced cartographic materials in participatory design workshops.

Based on an experience that reverberates in the field of counter-mapping, particularly in scenarios of invisibility of informal areas and absences, especially in terms of fundamental rights, it has been found that the integration of geotechnologies and participatory mapping allows for the construction of a fundamental database and thematic maps based on collected and produced field information

(territorial organization, housing precarity, geological-geotechnical risks, flooding risks, work patterns, public spaces, and potential housing areas, among others). Simultaneously, the RPAS survey technique has proven to be a powerful instrument with remarkable potential for social impact by giving an active voice to the community, especially with the support of geotechnologies. This is further enhanced by the simplicity of RPAS operation, low cost, and ease of application and replication.

As highlighted by Mogel and Bhagat (2007) as cited in Mesquita (2013), resistance to cartographic authority occurs not only by unveiling and interpreting shortcomings, effects, and intentions but also, above all, by constructing alternative maps that align with our interests and political, social, and environmental struggles.

Indeed, participatory mapping stands as an alternative and multidisciplinary tool for empowerment, guaranteeing fundamental rights and territorial sovereignty, and remains a particular challenge within academic circles.

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